

OPTIMIZATION AFTER EXTRACTION IN THE ORTHODONTIC TREATMENT OF OCCLUSAL ANOMALIES

Rakhmanova Dilfuza Ravilievna
Rakhmanova Nodiraoy Rustamovna
Samarkand State Medical University
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14062561>

Annotation

In this thesis, the methods of ensuring the optimal location of teeth through the effective use of the postextraction space were studied. The importance of this method in determining the optimal force and directions for moving teeth, keeping teeth in a stable position in a new location, and improving the patient's tooth row and occlusion structure was analyzed. Research results show that individual planning and mechanical modifications can optimize tooth movement, which is an important factor in improving oral anatomy and aesthetics.

Introduction: Orthodontic treatment of occlusion anomalies often involves the need to use post-extraction space to achieve correct tooth positioning and harmonize dental arches. Proper planning and use of this space can reduce treatment time and increase its effectiveness, minimizing unwanted effects.

The significant prevalence, progressive nature of the course, the presence of morphological, functional, and aesthetic disorders, often combined with internal pathology, with a high probability of developing local and systemic complications confirm the scientific, practical, medical and social significance of studies of dental anomalies (DA), which are one of the most significant pathologies in the structure of dental morbidity in children. According to modern scientific provisions, DA are the result of endogenously or exogenously conditioned errors in the implementation of the hereditary morphogenesis program, and almost all DA are hereditary or sporadic. Anomalies of the dental system can occur as a result of disturbances in the proliferative activity of cells, cell migration and normal movement of organs, cell differentiation and their physiological death, as well as adhesive mechanisms.

Objective of the study: To study methods for optimizing tooth movement in the post-extraction space, aimed at reducing treatment time, improving aesthetic results and minimizing the risks of damage to bone tissue and gums.

Materials and methods of the study

The object of the study were 38 patients of the first period of mature age, who had individual teeth extracted for orthodontic reasons. The patients were divided into two groups. The first (or main) group included 18 patients, who had a post-extraction space formed after tooth extraction using various methods. Patients of the second group (20 people) refused the proposed surgical treatment methods, and they underwent orthodontic treatment using generally accepted methods. Patients of both groups underwent orthodontic treatment using modern methods of fixed edgewise technique. The basis of surgical treatment methods for patients of the main group was the method of filling the socket of the extracted tooth with bone-plastic materials. We proposed to form a post-extraction space simultaneously with the extraction of a permanent tooth for orthodontic reasons.

Results of the study and their discussion

As a result of the conducted studies, it was established that the first premolars were extracted in most patients. As a rule, orthodontic treatment was carried out one month after

the extraction of teeth. In this regard, we studied the condition of the alveolar ridge of the post-extraction space in patients of both groups.

Summary

The issue of optimizing the movement of teeth into the postextraction space is important in the correction of anomalies in tooth occlusion during orthodontic treatment. Research shows that specific and planned actions are necessary to maintain and restore the correct alignment of teeth.

The process of optimally moving teeth in the postextraction space often requires additional forces and methods. Treatment results can be improved by controlling tooth movement, properly filling cavities, and using optimal approaches. Therefore, with the help of diagnostics, individual planning, modern devices and techniques, the possibility of problem-free placement of teeth increases. This provides painless and effective treatment of patients and complete elimination of orthodontic problems.

References:

1. Персин Л. С. Ортодонтия. Современные методы диагностики зубочелюстно-лицевых аномалий: Руководство для врачей. – М.: Информ. книга, 2007. – 248 с.
2. Персин Л. С. Стоматология детского возраста / Л. С. Персин, В. М. Елизарова, С. В. Дьякова // Учебная литература для медицинских вузов. – Изд. 5-е, перераб. и доп. – М.: «Медицина», 2006. – 640 с.
3. Тугарин В. А. Современная несъемная ортодонтическая техника эджуайс / В. А. Тугарин, Л. С. Персин, А. Ю. Порохин. – М.: Медицинская книга, 2006. – 220 с.
4. Хорошилкина Ф. Я. Ортодонтия. – М.: Медицинское информационное агентство, 2006. – 541 с.
5. BeGole E. A., Fox D. L., Sadowsky C. Analysis of change in arch form with premolar expansion // American journal of orthodontics and dentofacial orthopedics. – 1998. – № 113. – P. 307–315.